

Ursolic acid alleviates vascular calcification through DECR1-Mediated NF- κ B/NLRP3 signaling pathway

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Abstract

Vascular calcification is a common pathological feature in atherosclerosis, diabetes, chronic kidney disease and aging, and is associated with increased incidence of cardiovascular events and all-cause mortality. However, effective treatments for vascular calcification remain lacking. Ursolic acid, a naturally occurring compound abundantly found in apple peels and known for its potent anti-inflammatory properties, has not been previously explored in vascular calcification. In the present study, ursolic acid (UA) inhibited osteogenic differentiation and calcification of vascular smooth muscle cells (VSMCs) *in vitro*, and reduced calcification in human arterial rings *ex vivo*. Furthermore, UA attenuated aortic calcification in CKD rats and vitamin D3-overloaded mice. Mechanistically, ursolic acid targeted 2,4-dienoyl-CoA reductase 1 (DECR1), leading to its degradation and the subsequent inhibition of the NF- κ B/NLRP3 signaling pathway. This resulted in reduced expression of downstream inflammatory mediators such as cleaved Caspase-1 and IL-1 β . DECR1 expression was upregulated in calcified human VSMCs, arterial rings, and CKD rat aortas. DECR1 knockdown alleviated calcification, and its overexpression aggravated calcification in VSMCs and aortic rings. This study for the first time establishes the inhibitory effects of ursolic acid on vascular calcification and identifies DECR1 as a key mediator in this process, offering new insights for potential therapeutic strategies.

Introduction

Vascular calcification is a pathological phenomenon characterized by the ectopic deposition of hydroxyapatite crystals within arterial walls. It is recognized as an independent risk factor for cardiovascular events and all-cause mortality¹. Medial calcification in blood vessels is associated with diabetes, chronic kidney disease (CKD), and aging, leading to arterial remodeling and increased arterial stiffness²⁻⁴. This process disrupts hemodynamics, ultimately impairing end-organ perfusion and contributing to subsequent ischemic events and heart

failure⁵. The molecular mechanisms of vascular calcification involve the phenotypic transition of vascular smooth muscle cells (VSMCs) from a contractile to an osteogenic state, characterized by the upregulation of osteogenic markers such as runt-related transcription factor 2 (RUNX2), bone morphogenetic protein-2 (BMP2), and the downregulation of contractile markers such as smooth muscle α actin (α -SMA) and smooth muscle 22 alpha protein (SM22 α)^{6,7}. This process is driven by diverse pathological stimuli, including metabolic disturbances, inflammation, oxidative stress, and aging⁸⁻¹¹. In the context of CKD-associated vascular calcification, inflammation has been recognized as a key mechanism¹². The pro-inflammatory transcription factor NF- κ B is an important mediator linking inflammation to vascular calcification^{13,14}. NF- κ B/NLRP3 inflammatory signaling amplifies inflammatory responses by promoting Caspase-1 cleavage and interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β) maturation, further accelerating calcification^{15,16}. Despite ongoing research, the precise mechanisms underlying vascular calcification remain incompletely understood, and no established clinical therapies are currently available to specifically target vascular calcification.

Ursolic acid (UA) is a pentacyclic triterpenoid compound found in the fruits and medicinal herbs¹⁷. UA and its derivatives have been reported to display diverse biological properties and exert broad protective effects against metabolic disorders, obesity, cardiovascular diseases, cancer, and neurological diseases¹⁸. UA has attracted increasing interest as a candidate therapeutic agent due to its prominent anti-inflammatory and cardiovascular-protective activities¹⁹. Oral administration of UA significantly reduces blood pressure in high-fat diet-fed mice and spontaneously hypertensive rats^{20,21}. Previous studies have demonstrated that UA can prevent leptin-induced proliferation of VSMCs and attenuate neointimal hyperplasia in rat carotid artery injury models^{22,23}. UA also attenuates atherosclerosis in high-fat diet-fed ApoE^{-/-} mice through modulation of the ROS/NF- κ B pathway²⁴. Given the prominent role of inflammation in vascular calcification, we hypothesized that UA might inhibit vascular calcification.

In our study, unbiased drug target screening identified 2,4-dienoyl-CoA reductase 1 (DEC1) as a direct target of UA. DEC1 is considered as a rate-limiting enzyme involved in the

mitochondrial β -oxidation of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA)^{25,26}. It has been reported that DECR1 plays a crucial role in lipid metabolism, and knockdown of DECR1 leads to elevated levels of unsaturated fatty acids^{27,28}. Clinical evidence has suggested that supplementing with omega-3 PUFA can reduce cardiovascular events, with eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) showing particular effectiveness in secondary coronary prevention²⁹. Additionally, unsaturated fatty acid intake has been associated with reduced vascular calcification in a cross-sectional study³⁰. Moreover, unsaturated fatty acid intake can inhibit calcification process³¹. To date, the role of DECR1 in vascular calcification remains unknown.

In this study, we for the first time demonstrate that UA attenuates vascular calcification by targeting inflammatory pathway. We showed that UA significantly inhibits vascular calcification using *in vitro* and *in vivo* models. Furthermore, we showed that UA binds to DECR1, induces its ubiquitin-proteasome degradation, and thereby suppresses the NF- κ B/NLRP3 axis.

Methods

Reagents and antibodies

Chemical reagents, such as dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO), β -glycerophosphate (β -GP), calcium chloride (CaCl_2), SDS, and Tris-base were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). The fetal bovine serum (FBS), cell culture media, and antibiotics were purchased from Invitrogen (Grand Island, NY, USA). UA (MedChemExpress, USA) was dissolved in DMSO as stock solution at 50 mM and stored at -20°C .

Antibodies against cleaved Caspase-1 (#89332, IB: 1:1000), pro-IL-1 β (#12703, IB: 1:1000), NF- κ B p65 (#8242, IB: 1:1000, IF: 1:200), Phospho-NF- κ B p65 (#3033, IB: 1:1000), Runx2 (#12556, IB: 1:1000) were obtained from Cell Signaling Technology. Antibodies against BMP2 (ab284387, IB: 1:2000) and NLRP3 (ab263899, IB: 1:1000) were purchased from Abcam. Antibodies against α -SMA (14395-1-AP, IB: 1:1000), HIBCH (14603-1-AP, IB: 1:1000), Myc tag (16286-1-AP, IB: 1:1000), and Flag tag (20543-1-AP, IB: 1:1000) were purchased from Proteintech. Antibodies against Caspase-1 (WL02996, IB: 1:1000) and mature-IL-1 β

(WL00891, IB: 1:1000) were purchased from Wanleibio. DECR1 (E-AB-13189, IB: 1:1000, IHC: 1:100) antibody was obtained from ElabScience. Horseradish peroxidase (HRP)-conjugated antibodies against β -actin (HRP-66009, IB: 1:10000), rabbit IgG (SA00001-2, IB: 1:10000), and mouse IgG (SA00001-1, IB: 1:10000) were purchased from Proteintech.

Cell lines and cell culture

Human aortic smooth muscle cells (HCRL-1999) and human embryonic kidney 293T cells (HEK 293T; CRL-11268) was obtained from American Type Culture Collection (Manassas, VA, USA). All VSMCs between passages 3 and 8 were used in this study and cultured in growth medium in a 37 °C incubator with a humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO₂. The growth medium consisted of high glucose Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM), 10% FBS, 100 U/ml penicillin, and 100 μ g/ml streptomycin. Vascular calcification was induced by calcifying medium containing 10 mM β -glycerophosphate (β -GP) and 3 mM CaCl₂ added to the GM.

To investigate the effect of UA on vascular calcification, UA at different concentrations varying from 0.2 to 1 μ M were applied to treat VSMCs in the presence of CM. In some experiments, MG132 (100 nM, HY-13259; MedChemExpress), *chloroquine* (20 μ M, HY-17589A, MedChemExpress), *cycloheximide* 50 μ M, HY-12320, MedChemExpress) or nigericin (5 μ M, HY-127019, MedChemExpress) was used to treat VSMCs.

Arterial organ culture

Two-month-old Sprague–Dawley rats were euthanized via intraperitoneal injection of sodium pentobarbital (150 mg/kg) and thoracic aortas were isolated. Human tibial arteries were procured from patients who underwent amputation surgery. Written informed consent was obtained from all patients included in this study. Human tissue use in this study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Zhujiang Hospital, Southern Medical University, China (Approval number: 2021-KY-079-02) and complies with the Declaration of Helsinki. The characteristics of the donors are listed in Supplementary Table 2. Rat and human arteries were cut into 2–3 mm lengths and cultured in growth medium in a 37 °C incubator with a humidified atmosphere

containing 5% CO₂. CM containing 10 mM of β -GP and 3 mM of CaCl₂ was used to induce calcification in arterial rings for 14 days.

Animal studies

Eight-week-old male Sprague–Dawley rats and seven-week-old male C57BL/6J mice were purchased from the Central Animal Care Facility of Southern Medical University, China. All animals were housed in an environmentally controlled room (22–25 °C, 12 h light/dark cycle) with free access to food and water. To establish the CKD model, rats were received 5/6 nephrectomy as we previously reported^{32–34}. Briefly, anesthesia was induced via intraperitoneal injection of 50 mg/kg sodium pentobarbital. A 2/3 right nephrectomy was performed a week before left kidney removal. Two weeks after surgery, blood samples were collected from the orbital vein to detect creatinine levels. Rats were fed a high calcium and phosphorus diet (4% calcium, 1.8% phosphate) and received calcitriol (1 μ g/kg, Aladdin, China) via gastric perfusion for 4 weeks to induce aortic calcification. For compound treatment, rats were given UA (80 mg/kg/day) by gavage during the 4-week induction period. C57BL/6J mice were received 5 \times 10⁵ IU/kg vitamin D3 (Sigma-Aldrich) subcutaneously for three consecutive days, with the treatment of UA (150 mg/kg/day) via gastric perfusion during the three-day induction period and the following six days. All experiments were approved by the Institutional Animal Care Committee at Zhujiang Hospital, Southern Medical University, China (Approval number: LAEC-2023-057) and performed in accordance with the US NIH Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals (8th Edition, 2011).

Assessment of calcification

For cell staining, VSMCs were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) for 10 min and stained with 2% alizarin red (pH 4.2; Solarbio, China) for 5 min at room temperature. Excess dye was removed with deionized water and the cells were photographed under a Leica inverted microscope (Leica Microsystems, Germany). To quantitatively analyze the extent of calcification, alizarin red dye was incubated with 10% formic acid for 5 min, and the optical density at 405 nm was measured by a microplate reader. For arterial ring staining, the arterial segments were fixed in 10% formalin and embedded in paraffin. The tissues were then cut into

4- μ m-thick sections on a microtome and stained with 2% alizarin red for 5 min. Images were captured using an inverted microscope and analyzed using ImageJ (NIH, USA). For the staining of whole mount aorta, aortic arteries were fixed in 10% formalin for 24 h and then stained with 0.003% Alizarin Red solution in 1% potassium hydroxide (KOH) overnight. Aortas were then washed twice with 2% KOH and photographed using an inverted microscope. The calcium deposition of cells and tissues was decalcified by HCl and subjected to colorimetric analysis using a calcium assay kit (ElabScience, China) in accordance with the manufacturer's protocol. The calcium levels in each group were normalized to the protein content.

Micro-computed tomography

Micro-computed tomography (micro-CT; Siemens Inveon, Germany) was utilized to detect mineralization in the aortas of CKD rats. At the end of the animal experiments, aortas were isolated from rats sacrificed by intraperitoneal injection of sodium pentobarbital (150 mg/kg) and were fixed with 10% formalin. Micro-CT was used to scan aortas at a resolution of 0.079 mm and the Inveon research workplace software (Siemens Inveon, Germany) was used to analyze images.

Alkaline phosphatase activity assay

Alkaline phosphatase activity was determined using an ALP activity assay kit (Beyotime, Shanghai, CN) according to the manufacturer's protocol. In brief, cells were freeze-thawed in 0.1% Triton X-100 in PBS to extract proteins. Protein concentration was quantified using a BCA protein assay kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). Protein samples were incubated with the p-nitrophenylphosphate (p-NPP) substrate for 10 min at 37 °C, and the reactions were terminated with 3 M NaOH. The optical density was recorded at 405 nm and ALP activity was shown as units/mg protein.

Quantitative RT-PCR

Total RNA was extracted from HVSMCs using TRIzol reagent (Thermo Fisher Scientific) and reverse-transcribed using the PrimeScript RT Reagent Kit (TaKaRa, Shiga, Japan) following the manufacturer's instructions. The Real-Time PCR amplification was then performed as 40

cycles of 95 °C for 30 s, 60 °C for 30 s, and 72 °C for 30 s on 7500 Fast Real-Time PCR System (Applied Biosystems, Thermo Fisher Scientific) using SYBR Green mixture (TaKaRa). β -actin were used as loading control to normalize mRNA expression. The threshold cycle (CT) values were provided at the end of PCR. The relative transcriptional level of target genes normalized to β -actin expression was calculated by the comparative $2^{-\Delta\Delta CT}$ method. The PCR primers were as follows: β -actin (forward): CATGTACGTTGCTATCCAGGC, β -actin (reverse): CTCCTTAATGTCACGCACGAT; DECR1 (forward): CTGGACCCAACTGGAACATTT, DECR1 (reverse): GCAGCAAGATTTGCGAGTTCT. HIBCH (forward): GGTTGCACGGGAGTCATAACA, HIBCH (reverse): CTTTTCAGCTTCCGAGATCACT.

Western blotting

Whole cell lysates were prepared using RIPA lysis buffer containing proteinase and phosphatase inhibitors, homogenized and centrifuged at 12,000 \times g for 15 min at 4 °C. Protein concentration of cell lysates was determined by BCA protein assay kit. Cell lysates were incubated in SDS-PAGE sample loading buffer for 5 min at 100 °C, separated by 6%–12.5% SDS-PAGE, transferred to polyvinylidene difluoride membrane (Millipore), blocked with 5% non-fat milk powder for 2 h and incubated with primary antibodies specific for target proteins overnight and HRP-conjugated secondary antibodies for 2 h at room temperature. Chemiluminescence signals were detected by the imaging system (Amersham Imager 600, UK) and the relative protein expression level was normalized to β -actin expression.

Immunofluorescence

HVSMCs were washed with PBS, fixed in 4% PFA for 10 min, and permeabilized with 0.5% Triton X-100 for 15 min at room temperature. The tissues were fixed, embedded, and subjected to immunofluorescence analysis as described previously³⁵. Briefly, after incubating at 65 °C for 1 h, the tissue slides were submersed into sodium citrate buffer (10 mM, pH 6.0) and boiled for 10 min for 10 min. Cells and tissue slides were then blocked with 10% goat serum in PBS for 1 h at room temperature and incubated with primary antibody in BSA solution in a humidified chamber overnight at 4 °C. On the next day, cells and tissue slides were incubated with DAPI (Molecular Probes, Thermo Fisher Scientific) and Alexa Fluor-labeled secondary antibodies for

1 h at room temperature. Images were captured by confocal microscopy.

Histology and immunohistochemistry

Rat kidney samples were harvested at the indicated time point and fixed in 10% formalin solution. Fixed samples were embedded in paraffin and sectioned, and then sequentially deparaffinized, rehydrated, and stained with either Modified Masson's Trichrome Stain Kit (Solarbio Life Science, Beijing, CN) or Periodic Acid Schiff Stain Kit (Solarbio Life Science) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Images were captured under a Leica Microsystems microscope.

For the immunohistochemical staining, tissue sections were stained using a Ready-to-use Strep-Avidin Biotin Complex (SABC)-POD (rabbit IgG) kit and a DAB Chromogenic Substrate Kit (BOSTER Biological Technology, China) following the manufacturer's protocols. Briefly, tissue slides were incubated at 65 °C for 1 h, submerged in sodium citrate buffer (10 mM, pH 6.0), and boiled for 10 min. Subsequently, slides were incubated in 3% H₂O₂ for 10 min. Blocking was performed with 5% BSA at 37 °C for 30 min, followed by incubation with the primary antibody in a humidified chamber overnight at 4 °C. The slides were then hybridized with a biotinylated secondary antibody at 37 °C for 30 min and treated with SABC HRP-conjugated reagents at 37 °C for 30 min. Next, DAB reagent was applied to the samples, which were incubated in the dark at room temperature for 10 min. Hematoxylin was used for counterstaining. Images were captured using an inverted microscope.

Plasmid transfection

The Myc-ubiquitin and 3×Flag-DEC1 expression vectors constructed based on pcDNA3.1 vector were obtained from Vigene Biosciences (Shanghai, CN). HEK293T cells were transfected with the above plasmids using polyethyleneimine (PEI MW40000, 40816ES02, Yeasen Biotechnology, Shanghai, CN) in Opti-MEM medium (Invitrogen).

Small interfering RNA transfection

The target siRNA sequences against DEC1 (si-DEC1, forward: 5'-

GCGAUGCUACCACCUAAUATT-3', reverse: 5'-UAUUAGGUGGUAGCAUCGCTT-3') , HIBCH (si-HIBCH, forward: 5'-CGGGAGUCAUAACACUAAATT-3', reverse: 5'-UUUAGUGUUAUGACUCCCGTT-3'), and the scrambled siRNA (si-NC, negative control) were synthesized by Tsingke Biotech Co (Beijing, CN). When reaching 70–80% confluence, cells were transfected with 30 nM siRNA using lipofectamine RNAiMAX (Invitrogen) in Opti-MEM medium according to the manufacturer's protocols. Knockdown efficiency of siRNA was verified by western blot analysis at 48 h post-transfection.

Recombinant adenovirus transfection

Recombinant adenovirus encoding GFP (negative control) or DECR1 were purchased from Vigene Biosciences. HVSMCs were seeded in 35 mm dishes and cultured in GM to reach 80% confluence. HVSMCs were infected with adenovirus diluted in the GM with an optimal multiplicity of infection (MOI = 50) for 24 h. Overexpression efficiency of adenovirus was verified by western blot 2 days after infection.

For the *in vivo* adenovirus studies, rats were received 5/6 nephrectomy. Briefly, rats were randomly divided into 4 groups: namely, Sham with GFP adenovirus (Ad/GFP) group, Sham with DECR1 adenovirus (Ad/DECR1) group, CKD with Ad/GFP group, and CKD with Ad/DECR1 group. Anesthesia was induced via intraperitoneal injection of 50 mg/kg sodium pentobarbital. A 2/3 right nephrectomy was performed a week before left kidney removal. The infrarenal segment of the abdominal aorta was exposed under anesthesia via a midline incision during the second sham surgery or left nephrectomy. The left renal artery was used as a marker, and the abdominal aorta was exposed ~2.0 cm above it. Then we applied Ad/GFP or Ad/DECR1 in 30% F-127 Pluronic gel (Sigma-Aldrich; 200 μ l, 5×10^9 PFU/ml) solution perivascularly to the exposed abdominal aortic segments. The incision was sutured after the hydrogel was solidified. Two weeks after surgery, rats were fed a high calcium and phosphorus diet (4% calcium, 1.8% phosphate) and received calcitriol (1 μ g/kg, Aladdin, China) via gastric perfusion for 4 weeks to induce aortic calcification.

CCK8 cell viability assay

Cell viability was measured using the Cell Counting Kit-8 (CCK8; DOJINDO, Kumamoto, Japan) assay. The HVSMCs were suspended with 100 μ L of GM, seeded into 96-well plates (3000 cells/well). After 12 h, the medium was removed, and 100 μ L of fresh medium containing 0.1% DMSO or different concentrations of UA as indicated was added to culture plates and incubated for 4 days. After the addition of 10 μ L of CCK8 to each well, the incubation continued for 2 h in a cell incubator. The cell proliferation was measured by reading the OD value at 450 nm using a microplate reader.

RNA sequencing

Total RNA of HVSMCs was extracted using TRIzol reagents and RNA quality was determined using an Agilent 2100 Bioanalyser (Agilent, Santa Clara, CA, USA). RNA was then subjected to RNA-seq analysis on a BGISEQ-500 system (BGI, Shenzhen, PR China) after reverse transcription. The gene expression level was calculated using the Fragment Per Kilobase of Million mapped reads (FPKM) method. Differential expression was assessed using the DEGseq package. Genes with a *Q* value less than 0.05 were considered as differentially expressed genes (DEGs). Enrichment ratios in KEGG analyses were calculated as term candidate gene number divided by term gene number. GSEA was conducted to identify consistent changes in molecular signaling pathways using Reactome Pathway Database (V89 Released). The RNA-seq data can be accessed through the NCBI Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) Repository using accession number GSE276910.

Cellular thermal shift assay

CETSA using living cells was conducted as described previously^{36,37}. Briefly, cells were treated with DMSO or 100 μ M UA for 2 h, and then cells were collected and resuspended in PBS supplemented with protease inhibitors. Each aliquot was heated at indicated temperatures for 3 min on PCR cycler (Bio-Rad, CA, USA). The cells were lysed by three freeze/thaw cycles consisting of thawing the samples in a heat block set to 25 $^{\circ}$ C accompanied by mixing them several times by inversion and then shock freezing them again in liquid nitrogen. The samples were centrifuged and the supernatants were subjected to immunoblotting analysis.

For CETSA using cell extracts, cells were collected and resuspended in PBS, and lysed by three freeze/thaw cycles as described above. DMSO and UA, used for treatment of living cells, were added to the 1.5 ml aliquots of cell extracts. After mixing and incubation (1 h, 37 °C), the extracts were distributed into 100 µL each in PCR tube strips. After a brief centrifugation using a benchtop centrifuge, the temperature treatment at different temperatures was performed as described above.

For ITDR-CETSA, cells were treated with UA at different concentrations varying from 10 nM to 1 mM for 2 h, and then cells were collected, resuspended in PBS, heated at a single indicated temperature for 3 min, and lysed by three freeze/thaw cycles. The constant treatment temperature was selected from the melting curves of CETSA in order to obtain the largest possible average difference in signal intensity for the proteins between treatment with the inhibitor and the DMSO control.

For tissue-CETSA, rats were dosed in gavage with vehicle or 80mg/kg UA. 3 hours after gavage, rats were killed and aortas were dissected into pieces. Samples were weighed and heat treated at 37 or 62 °C for 3 min in PBS buffer. After three freeze/thaw cycles, tissue samples were disrupted using ceramic beads, then centrifuged and the supernatants were subjected to immunoblotting analysis.

Synthesis of biotinylated ursolic acid and streptavidin–biotin affinity pull-down assay

For synthesis of biotinylated UA (biotin-UA), 0.2 mmol of biotin-dPEG4-NH₂ was weighed and transferred to a 20 mL glass vial with a stir bar. Subsequently, 0.182 mmol of EDC hydrochloride, 0.182 mmol of 1-Hydroxybenzotriazole, and 0.9 mmol of N, N-diisopropylethylamine were added. Then, 20 mL of ethanol and acetonitrile mixture (1:1) was added, ultrasonicated for dissolution, and stirred at room temperature at 800 rpm for 4 hours. Afterward, 0.2 mmol of UA was added and ultrasonicated again for dissolution, followed by stirring at room temperature at 800 rpm for 16 hours. The reaction was monitored by thin-layer chromatography using an ethyl acetate: methanol: water (8:1:1) solvent system. Upon completion, the reaction mixture was mixed with pre-weighed silica gel and solvent evaporated

using a rotary evaporator at 50 °C and 0.1 MPa. The dried mixture was loaded onto a silica gel column and eluted with ethyl acetate: methanol: water (8:1:1). The eluate containing the target compound was concentrated, transferred to a 1.5 mL EP tube, and vacuum-dried to yield 20 mg of a light-yellow solid. The dried compound, biotin-UA, was sealed and stored at -20 °C.

HVSMCs were lysed with PBS containing 1% protease inhibitor cocktail by three freeze/thaw cycles same as previously described. The cell lysate was incubated with free biotin (5 μ M, Aladdin), biotin-UA (5 μ M), or a combination of biotin-UA (5 μ M) and biotin (20 μ M) at 4 °C for 5 h. Subsequently, the pre-washed streptavidin agarose beads (Beyotime) were added to the system as above and incubated overnight at 4 °C with rotation. The beads were washed three times with elution buffer then suspended in 1 \times SDS-PAGE sample loading buffer. After denaturation at 100 °C for 5 min, the samples were analyzing by western blot.

Co-immunoprecipitation assay

HEK293T cells were transfected with Myc-Ubiquitin and Flag-DEC1R1 plasmid DNA and subjected to UA treatment as indicated. After washed twice with PBS, cells were lysed in IP buffer containing protease inhibitor cocktail for 30 min. Cell lysates were centrifuged and supernatant was incubated with anti-flag magnetic beads (Selleck, USA) overnight at 4 °C. The precipitates were washed 3 times with PBST buffer followed by suspending in 1 \times SDS-PAGE sample loading buffer. After denaturation at 100 °C for 5 min, the samples were analyzing by western blot.

Serum biochemical analysis

To analyze the biochemical parameters of CKD rats, we harvested venous blood from rats at the indicated time point of experiments. Serum levels of creatinine were determined using Creatinine Assay kit (BioAssay Systems, USA). Serum levels of aspartate aminotransferase (AST) and alanine aminotransferase (ALT) were measured on a the Mindray 330e full-automatic biochemical analyzer (Mindray, Shenzhen, CN).

Molecular dynamic simulation

The structure of mitochondrial 2,4-dienoyl-CoA reductase was retrieved from PDB entry 1W6U25²⁵. The 3D structure of UA was downloaded from the PubChem database and optimized using the MMFF94s force field of Avogadro software to obtain the optimal molecular structure with the lowest energy state. Autodock vina (v1.2.5) was used to dock the ligand to the binding pockets³⁸. The best poses were chosen to be the initial structures for the following molecular dynamics simulations by manually checking all the vina docking output.

The protein-ligand system was subjected to molecular dynamics simulation using GROMACS 2022 software³⁹. AMBER14SB and GAFF were selected as the protein force field and the ligand force field, respectively, while TIP3P water model was selected to add solvent to the protein ligand system⁴⁰. The LINCS algorithm was used to constrain bonds between heavy atoms and hydrogen to enable a time step of 2 fs⁴¹. A 1.2 nm cutoff was used for van der Waals interaction and short-range electrostatic interactions calculations, and the Particle Mesh Ewald method was implemented for long-range electrostatic calculations. Simulation temperature was maintained at 298 K using a V-rescale thermostat and 1 bar pressure using Parrinello-Rahman barostat^{42,43}. Pre-equilibration simulations are conducted at 298 K, with 100 ps of isothermal-isobaric (NVT) and isobaric-isothermal (NPT) simulations, followed by a production run of 100 ns, saving configurations every 10 ps. After the simulation, VMD and PyMOL software are used to analyze the simulation trajectories, and the g_mmpbsa tool is employed to calculate the MMPBSA binding free energy between the protein and small molecule ligand⁴⁴. The representative structures were taken as the center of the biggest cluster got from the gromos clustering method⁴⁵.

Mendelian Randomization

The DECR1 cis-eQTL data utilized in this study were sourced from published genome-wide association studies (GWAS) involving 151 multi-ancestry aortic smooth muscle cell donors⁴⁶. The GWAS data for blood pressure traits provided summary statistics for systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, and pulse pressure based on a large-scale trans-ancestry meta-analysis comprising 2,902,060 individuals from the Cardiovascular Disease Knowledge Portal. For the Mendelian Randomization analysis, we employed the TwoSampleMR R package

(version 0.5.8; <https://mrcieu.github.io/TwoSampleMR/>)⁴⁷.

Only single-nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) located within a ± 1 Mb window from the transcription start site of *DEC1* were considered as cis-eQTLs. SNPs meeting the significance threshold of $p < 1 \times 10^{-5}$ were identified as potential instrumental variables (IVs). To ensure the independence of the selected SNPs, a clumping procedure was applied, setting the linkage disequilibrium coefficient $R^2 < 0.1$ within a 500 kb window. Following these stringent criteria, only rs10956510 was identified as the independent SNP suitable for inclusion in the MR analysis.

Statistical analysis

All statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad prism 10.0 software. The data shown in the study were obtained from at least four independent experiments and all data in different experimental groups were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Statistical analyses were performed using student's t-test analysis or ANOVA. Details of each statistical analysis were provided in the figure legends. Differences with P -values < 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Results

Ursolic acid inhibits calcification of human vascular smooth muscle cells and arterial rings

To investigate the cell toxicity of UA, CCK-8 assay was performed and the results showed that UA at concentrations below 2 μ M did not induce any significant cytotoxicity in human VSMCs (HVSMCs) (Supplementary Fig. 1). We then treated HVSMCs with different concentrations of UA (0.2, 0.5, or 1 μ M) in calcifying medium (CM) to assess its effect on vascular calcification *in vitro*. Alizarin red staining showed that calcification was obvious in CM-treated cells, but not in cell treated with growth medium (GM), suggesting that VSMC calcification was successfully induced under osteogenic condition. UA addition resulted in reduced calcification compared to the CM-treated cells at day 7 (Fig. 1A), and this was further confirmed by quantification analysis of alizarin red staining (Fig. 1B). This reduction in calcium deposition was also

confirmed through calcium content assay (Fig. 1C). In addition, UA treatment decreased expression of the osteogenic markers RUNX2 and BMP2, accompanied by increase expressions of the contractile marker α -SMA (Fig. 1D). To investigate whether UA treatment has an effect on vascular calcification *ex vivo*, rat aortic rings and human arterial rings were incubated with UA under CM. As indicated by Alizarin red staining and quantification analysis, calcification of rat aortic rings was attenuated by UA at day 14 (Fig. 1E, F). Additionally, the calcium content of aortic rings was reduced after UA treatment (Fig. 1G). Consistently, Alizarin red staining revealed significant reductions in mineral deposition in UA-treated human arterial rings (Fig. 1H, I), which was corroborated by decreased calcium content (Fig. 1J). These findings collectively demonstrate that UA effectively inhibits vascular calcification *in vitro* and *ex vivo*.

Fig. 1 UA inhibits osteogenic differentiation of HVSMCs and reduces calcification of both HVSMCs and arterial rings. HVSMCs were cultured in growth medium (GM), calcifying medium (CM), or CM with UA (0.2, 0.5, or 1.0 μ M) for 7 days (A–D, n = 4). Rat aortic rings (E–G) and human arterial rings (H–J) were cultured in GM, CM, or CM with UA (0.2, 0.5, or

1.0 μM) for 14 days ($n = 4$). **A** Calcium deposition in HVSMCs was detected with alizarin red staining. Scale bar = 500 μM . **B** Quantification of alizarin red staining by a microplate reader. **C** Quantification of calcium content using a calcium assay kit. **D** Representative western blots showing RUNX2, BMP2, and α -SMA in HVSMCs, with quantification by densitometry. **E, H** Calcium deposition in rat aortic ring or human arterial ring sections was detected with alizarin red staining. Scale bar = 500 μm (upper) or 150 μm (lower). **F, I** Quantification of the area positive for Alizarin Red in the arterial rings by ImageJ software. **G, J** Quantification of calcium content by a calcium assay kit. Data were presented as mean \pm SD. One-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's test. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Ursolic acid inhibits aortic calcification *in vivo*

To assess the effect of UA on vascular calcification *in vivo*, CKD rats were treated with either vehicle or UA (Fig. 2A). Two-week post-surgery, serum creatinine levels were significantly elevated in both the CKD (vehicle-treated) and UA-treated groups compared to the sham group, with no significant difference between the CKD and UA groups (Fig. 2B). Meanwhile, Periodic Acid Schiff (PAS) and Masson staining of the left kidney revealed glomerulosclerosis and renal interstitial fibrosis, confirming the successful establishment of the CKD model (Fig. 2C). Notably, micro-CT analysis revealed a marked reduction in aortic calcification in the UA-treated group compared to the CKD group (Fig. 2D). Similarly, alizarin red staining of entire aortas and aortic sections also demonstrated decreased calcification in the aortas of UA-treated rats (Fig. 2E, F), which is consistent with the calcium content assay results (Fig. 2G). Furthermore, UA supplementation downregulated Runx2 and BMP2 expression levels and upregulated α -SMA (Fig. 2H). The activity of ALP, an osteogenic differentiation marker, was also reduced in the aortas of CKD rats treated with UA (Fig. 2I). Importantly, UA administration did not induce significant systemic toxicity, as evidenced by stable serum liver enzyme levels (AST, ALT) and maintained body weight (Supplementary Fig. 2). To further corroborate these findings, vitamin D3 (VitD3)-overloaded mice were treated with UA (Fig. 2J). Alizarin red staining of aortas and aortic sections showed that aortic calcification in mice was induced by VitD3, and attenuated by UA treatment (Fig. 2K, L). Consistently, the calcium content in the

aortas of VitD3-overloaded mice was reduced following UA treatment (Fig. 2M). Moreover, UA treatment led to the downregulation of Runx2 and BMP2 protein expression and the upregulation of α -SMA (Fig. 2N), along with a reduction in ALP activity in the aortas of VitD3-overloaded mice (Fig. 2O). Taken together, these findings demonstrate that UA effectively inhibits vascular calcification *in vivo*.

Figure 2

Fig. 2 UA inhibits aortic calcification in CKD rats and VitD3-overloaded mice. A Rats subjected to 5/6 nephrectomy (Nx) were treated with vehicle or UA (80 mg/kg/day) intragastrically (i.g.) for 4 weeks (B–I, n = 6). B Serum creatinine levels of rats were measured 2 weeks post-surgery by a creatinine assay kit. C Representative PAS and Masson staining of

rat renal tissue collected post-sacrifice. Scale bars = 100 μm (PAS) or 50 μm (Masson). **D** Micro-CT images of rat aortas. Scale bar = 10 mm. **E, K** Calcium deposition in aortas was detected with alizarin red staining. **F, L** Calcium deposition in aortic sections was detected with alizarin red staining. Scale bars = 500 μm (upper) or 150 μm (lower) for rat aortic sections; 150 μm (upper) or 50 μm (lower) for mouse aortic sections. **G, M** Quantification of calcium content in aortas using a calcium assay kit. **H, N** Representative western blots showing Runx2, BMP2, and α -SMA in aortas, with quantification by densitometry. **I, O** Quantification of aortic ALP activity. **J** Mice received VitD3 subcutaneously (s.c.) for three consecutive days were treated with UA (150 mg/kg/day, i.g.) during the three-day modeling period and for the following six days (K–O, n = 6). Data were presented as mean \pm SD. One-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's test. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

DECRI is the direct cellular target of ursolic acid against vascular calcification

To identify the cellular target of UA in inhibiting vascular calcification, we analyzed the published two-dimensional thermal proteome profiling (2D-TPP) data for UA^{48,49}. As demonstrated in [Fig. 3A](#), we identified four proteins with FDR < 0.05. Among these, DECRI was particularly notable for its highest significance in both our analysis and previous threshold-based analyses⁴⁹. We also noted that HIBCH was the second most significant protein in previous analyses with a high affinity for UA by molecular docking, although it did not reach significance in our FDR-based analysis⁴⁹. Based on these analyses, we propose that DECRI and HIBCH are the most likely protein targets mediating the protective effects of UA against vascular calcification.

To confirm the direct cellular target of UA, we conducted a cellular thermal shift assay (CETSA) to evaluate the thermal stability of DECRI and HIBCH in HVSMCs following UA treatment. To distinguish the direct and indirect effects, CETSA was performed using cell extracts instead of living cells⁵⁰. Of interest, CETSA results showed that UA altered the thermal stability of both HIBCH (increased at 57°C) and DECRI (decreased at 52–62°C) in both living cells and cell lysates ([Fig. 3B, C](#)). We then performed isothermal dose-response CETSA (ITDR-CETSA)

experiments to obtain concentration-dependent characteristics of the small molecule–protein interactions in living cells. UA exhibited a higher potency for DECR1 ($EC_{50} = 0.736 \mu\text{M}$) than for HIBCH ($EC_{50} = 23.0 \mu\text{M}$) in HVSMCs (Supplementary Fig. 3). Subsequently, we used another orthogonal target identification technology, streptavidin–biotin affinity pull-down assay, to validate whether UA binds to its targets. Western blotting of biotin-UA (Fig. 3D) pull-down samples confirmed the binding of UA to DECR1 and HIBCH (Fig. 3E). Competitive experiment showed that UA could competitively bind to DECR1 and HIBCH with a $5 \mu\text{M}$ biotin-UA.

To determine the roles of DECR1 and HIBCH in vascular calcification, we used specific small interfering RNA (siRNA) to knockdown DECR1 or HIBCH in HVSMCs, and both DECR1 and HIBCH were successfully knockdown (Fig. 3F, G). DECR1 knockdown showed an inhibitory effect on vascular calcification, but HIBCH knockdown had no significant effect, confirming DECR1 as the primary target (Fig. 3H-K). Besides, DECR1 knockdown decreased in RUNX2 and BMP2 protein levels and increased in α -SMA (Fig. 3L).

Thermal shift assay (TSA) is based on the well-known biophysical phenomenon of ligand-induced conformational stabilization of proteins⁵¹. ITDR-TSA using UA and recombinant purified His-DECR1 protein showed enhanced thermal stability at high UA concentrations ($EC_{50} = 5.626 \mu\text{M}$, Fig. 3M), indicating a direct interaction between UA and DECR1. To further validate this interaction *in vivo*, we employed a tissue-CETSA to assess the binding of UA to DECR1 in rat aortas. At 62°C , DECR1 was markedly stabilized in the aortas of UA-treated rats (Fig. 3N).

Subsequently, we performed molecular docking and dynamics simulations to investigate how UA interacts with DECR1. Molecular docking revealed strong UA-DECR1 interaction (-9.8 kcal/mol) involving salt bridges (Arg91) and hydrophobic contacts (Thr69, Asn148, Phe249, Arg251) (Fig. 3O). The results of the molecular dynamics simulation indicated that after 20 ns' structural adjustment, the root mean square deviation of the complex fluctuated around 0.4 nm and remained stable and tightly bound in 100 ns (Supplementary Figure 4). As dynamics

simulations indicated, the critical residues between UA and DECR1 with the top three average energy values were Arg251, Arg91, and Lys92. Together, these findings support a robust and stable interaction between UA and DECR1, with key residues potentially contributing to its biological activity.

Figure 3

Fig. 3 DECR1 is the direct target of UA against vascular calcification. **A** Volcano plot of the 2D-TPP dataset obtained from the treatment of SKBR3 cell lysates with UA. Proteins with

an FDR < 0.05 are labeled by name. **B** Representative western blots of CETSA showing UA binding to DECR1 and HIBCH in both HVSMCs and HVSMC lysates. HVSMCs or HVSMC lysates were incubated with DMSO or 100 μ M UA for 1 h and heated at 37–67 $^{\circ}$ C (n = 4). **C** Quantification of non-denatured DECR1 and HIBCH protein levels in HVSMCs or HVSMC lysates heated at 37–67 $^{\circ}$ C, based on western blot densitometry. **D** Chemical structure of the biotinylated UA (biotin-UA). **E** Representative western blots showing biotin-UA binding to DECR1 and HIBCH in HVSMC lysates. Biotin-streptavidin affinity purification experiments were conducted in HVSMC lysates using 5 μ M biotin (left lane), with the 5 μ M biotin-UA without UA (middle lane), and with 20 μ M UA (right lane, n = 4). **F** Representative western blot showing DECR1 expression in HVSMCs, with quantification by densitometry. HVSMCs were transfected with negative control siRNA (si-NC) or DECR1 siRNA (si-DECR1) in growth medium (GM) for 2 days (n = 4). **G** Representative western blot showing HIBCH expression in HVSMCs, with quantification by densitometry. HVSMCs were transfected with si-NC or HIBCH siRNA (si-HIBCH) in GM for 2 days (n = 4). **H** Calcium deposition in HVSMCs was detected with alizarin red staining. Scale bar = 500 μ M. After transfection with si-NC or si-DECR1, HVSMCs were cultured in GM or calcifying medium (CM) for 7 days (H, I, n = 4). **I**, **K** Quantification of calcium content using a calcium assay kit. **J** Calcium deposition in HVSMCs was detected with alizarin red staining. Scale bar = 500 μ M. After transfection with si-NC or si-HIBCH, HVSMCs were cultured in GM or CM for 7 days (J, K, n = 4). **L** Representative western blots showing RUNX2, BMP2, and α -SMA in HVSMCs, with quantification by densitometry. **M** Representative western blot of TSA analysis showing UA binding to purified his-DECR1 protein, with quantification by densitometry. His-DECR1 were incubated with 0–100 μ M UA for 1 h and heated at 62 $^{\circ}$ C (n = 4). EC50, median effective concentration. **N** Tissue-CETSA work flow for tissue samples derived from *in vivo* dosed rats (left panel). Rat aortas were collected and heated at 37 or 62 $^{\circ}$ C 3 hours after administering vehicle or 80mg/kg UA intragastrically (n = 3). Representative western blot of Tissue-CETSA showing UA binding to DECR1 *in vivo*, with quantification by densitometry (right panel). **O** Molecular docking of DECR1 and UA. Data were presented as mean \pm SD. Two-tailed Student unpaired t-test for **F**, **G**. One-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's test for **M**. Two-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's test for **I**, **K**, **L**. Two-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni test for **C**, **N**.

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, ns not significant. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

DEC1 protein expression is increased in vascular calcification

Furthermore, DEC1 protein levels were significantly elevated in CM-treated HVSMCs and human arterial rings compared to GM controls, as confirmed by western blot and immunohistochemistry (IHC) analyses (Fig. 4A-C). Proteomic data from an online database also showed a substantial upregulation of DEC1 in human coronary artery smooth muscle cells (HCASMCs) treated with osteogenic medium (OM) for 7 days compared to normal medium (NM, Fig. 4D)⁵². Consistently, Dec1 protein levels were elevated in calcified aortas of CKD rats, with IHC showing increased expression in VSMCs (Fig. 4E, F). Therefore, these results suggest a substantial increase in DEC1 protein levels during vascular calcification. Further investigation in a human plaque proteomic dataset confirmed higher DEC1 levels in calcified cores relative to peripheral regions (Fig. 4G). Subsequently, within the largest available individual-level plaque proteomics dataset, we identified a significant positive correlation between DEC1 protein expression and ALP protein levels ($p=0.038$, Fig. 4H)⁵³. Genetic analysis identified rs10956510 as the cis-eQTL most strongly associated with DEC1 expression in the aortas (8:90200334_G/T, $\beta=-0.264$, $p=8.126 \times 10^{-7}$, Fig. 4I)⁴⁶. Subsequently, Mendelian randomization showed that DEC1 reduction mediated by this variant causally decreases blood pressure parameters (Fig. 4J, Supplementary Table 1). Given that elevated pulse pressure is one of the adverse effects of vascular calcification^{54,55}, these findings indicated that DEC1 expression could influence blood pressure through affecting vascular calcification.

However, we observed that DEC1 mRNA expression was significantly reduced under CM conditions compared to GM (Supplementary Fig. 5A). DEC1 mRNA levels did not show a significant increase in CKD rats when compared to the controls ($p=0.208$, Supplementary Fig. 5B). For HCASMCs, there was no significant difference in DEC1 mRNA levels between NM and OM groups ($p>0.99$, Supplementary Fig. 5C). The failure to observe DEC1 expression upregulation in all models suggests that the increased DEC1 protein levels are not a result of transcriptional changes.

Figure 4

Fig. 4 DECR1 protein expression is increased in vascular calcification. **A** Representative western blot showing DECR1 in HVSMCs, with quantification by densitometry. HVSMCs were cultured in growth medium (GM) or calcifying medium (CM) for 4 days ($n = 4$). **B** Representative western blot showing DECR1 in human arterial rings, with quantification by densitometry. Human arterial rings were cultured in GM or CM for 7 or 14 days ($n = 4$). **C** Representative alizarin red staining and immunohistochemistry images of DECR1 in human arterial rings, with quantification by integrated option density (IOD, $n = 12$). Scale bars = 200 μm (left) or 50 μm (right). **D** Representative western blot showing Decr1 in rat aortas, with quantification by densitometry ($n = 6$). **E** Representative alizarin red staining and immunohistochemistry images of Decr1 in rat aortas, with quantification by IOD ($n = 12$). Scale bars = 200 μm (left) or 50 μm (right). **F** Quantification of DECR1 in human coronary artery smooth muscle cells (HCASMCs) over time, based on proteome dataset PXD022575 from ProteomeXchange database. HCASMCs were cultured in normal medium (NM) or osteogenic medium (OM) for different durations ($n = 2$). **G** Quantification of DECR1 in the core and periphery of human atherosclerotic plaques, based on proteome dataset PXD030975 from ProteomeXchange database. 219 samples (110 core and 109 periphery samples were obtained

from 120 patients undergoing carotid endarterectomy. **H** Correlation of the protein levels between DECR1 and ALPL were measured by Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) in PXD039077. The data is shown from 21 carotid atherosclerotic plaques. **I** Expression of DECR1 transcript by genotype in 151 human aortic smooth muscle cells. The number of individuals with genotype G/G, G/T, and T/T is 50, 52, and 43 (aorta); **J** Mendelian randomization revealed that reduced DECR1 levels were significantly associated with lower blood pressure traits. Data were presented as mean \pm SD. Two-tailed Student unpaired t-test for **A, B, D**. Mann-Whitney test for **C, E**. Two-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni for **F**. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

DECR1 overexpression aggravates vascular calcification *in vitro* and *in vivo*

To assess the role of DECR1 in VSMC calcification, HVSMCs were infected with Ad/DECR1, and DECR1 protein expression was significantly elevated 2 days post-infection (Fig. 5A). Alizarin red staining revealed DECR1 overexpression did not induce spontaneous calcification but amplified CM-induced calcium deposition (Fig. 5B). Consistently, Ad/DECR1-infected cells exhibited increased calcium deposition compared to Ad/GFP-infected cells (Fig. 5C). Additionally, DECR1 overexpression promoted osteogenic differentiation of HVSMCs, as indicated by upregulation of RUNX2 and BMP2 and downregulation of α -SMA (Fig. 5D). Next, we delivered Ad/DECR1 to CKD rat aortas, and DECR1 overexpression was verified by western blot (Fig. 5E). Of interest, DECR1 overexpression exacerbated calcification in CKD rat aortas (Figure 5F-G). In addition, DECR1 overexpression promoted expression of the osteogenic markers and suppressed the expression of contractile markers (Fig. 5H). Collectively, these findings demonstrate that DECR1 promotes osteogenic differentiation and aggravates vascular calcification both *in vitro* and *in vivo*.

Figure 5

Fig. 5 DEC1 overexpression aggravates vascular calcification *in vitro* and *in vivo*. **A** Representative western blot showing DEC1 expression in HVSMCs, with quantification by densitometry. HVSMCs were transfected with GFP adenovirus (Ad/GFP) or DEC1 adenovirus (Ad/DEC1) and cultured in growth medium (GM) for 2 days (n = 4). **B** Calcium deposition in HVSMCs was detected with alizarin red staining. Scale bar = 500 µm. After transfection with Ad/GFP or Ad/DEC1, HVSMCs were cultured in GM or calcifying medium (CM) for 7 days (B–D, n = 4). **C** Quantification of calcium content using a calcium assay kit. **D** Representative western blots showing RUNX2, BMP2, and α-SMA in HVSMCs, with quantification by densitometry. **E** Representative western blot showing DEC1 expression in rat abdominal aortas, with quantification by densitometry. Rat abdominal aortas were collected 2 days after transfection with Ad/GFP or Ad/DEC1 in 30% F-127 Pluronic gel (n = 3). **F** Calcium deposition in rat abdominal aortic sections was detected with alizarin red staining. Scale bar = 500 µm (upper) or 150 µm (lower). Abdominal aortas were collected from rats

subjected to sham surgery or 5/6 nephrectomy, following transfection with Ad/GFP or Ad/DEC1 in 30% F-127 Pluronic gel and a 4-week calcification induction (F–H, n = 6). **G** Quantification of calcium content in rat aortas using a calcium assay kit (n = 6). **H** Representative western blots showing Runx2, BMP2, and α -SMA in rat abdominal aortas, with quantification by densitometry. Data were presented as mean \pm SD. Two-tailed Student unpaired t-test for **A**, **E**. Two-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's test for **C**, **D**, **G**, **H**. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Ursolic acid inhibits vascular calcification via ubiquitin-proteasome-dependent DEC1 degradation

Given the identified interaction between UA and DEC1, we investigated whether UA affects DEC1 protein levels by treating HVSMCs with various concentrations of UA in the presence of CM. Compared to untreated cells, DEC1 protein levels were significantly decreased in the presence of CM (**Fig. 6A**). Moreover, 1 μ M UA reduced DEC1 protein levels in HVSMCs from 100% to 30% in a time-dependent manner (0–48 h, **Fig. 6B**). Notably, DEC1 mRNA levels remained unchanged, indicating that UA-induced downregulation of DEC1 protein was not due to transcriptional inhibition (**Fig. 6C**). In addition, UA administration significantly decreased Decr1 expression in aortic medial layer of CKD rats compared to vehicle administration (**Fig. 6J, K**). Furthermore, co-treatment with UA and CHX accelerated the degradation of DEC1 protein (**Fig. 6D**). The ubiquitin-proteasome system (UPS) is the main mean of intracellular protein degradation, responsible for much of the regulated proteolysis⁵⁶. Next, treatment with 1 μ M UA significantly increased the protein levels of polyubiquitinated Flag-DEC1 and reduced Flag-DEC1 (**Fig. 6E**). Additionally, treatment with the proteasomal inhibitor MG-132 markedly blocked the UA-induced reduction in DEC1 protein levels, but lysosomal inhibitor chloroquine (CQ) did not, highlighting the involvement of UPS system rather than the autophagy-lysosome pathway in the degradation process (**Fig. 6F**, **Supplementary Fig. 6**). To investigate the reversibility of UA-mediated DEC1 degradation, HVSMCs were treated with 1 μ M UA for 4 days, followed by washout. After 24 hours without UA, DEC1 protein levels returned to baseline (**Supplementary Fig. 7**). Furthermore, Alizarin red staining and calcium quantification demonstrated that UA inhibited calcification in

HVSMCs and aortic tissues, and this effect that was reversed by DECR1 overexpression (Fig. 6G, H), indicating DECR1 was involved in UA-mediated inhibition of vascular calcification. Consistently, the inhibition in osteogenic differentiation of HVSMCs by UA was reverse by DECR1 overexpression (Fig. 6I). In summary, our results indicate that UA promotes the polyubiquitination and subsequent degradation of DECR1, which mediate the inhibitory effect of UA on vascular calcification.

Figure 6

Fig. 6 UA down-regulates DECR1 expression via ubiquitin-dependent protein

degradation mode. **A** Representative western blot showing DECR1 expression in HVSMCs, with quantification by densitometry. HVSMCs were cultured in growth medium (GM), calcifying medium (CM), or CM with UA (0.2, 0.5, or 1.0 μ M) for 7 days (n = 4). **B** Representative western blot showing DECR1 expression in HVSMCs, with quantification by densitometry. HVSMCs were cultured in GM with 1 μ M UA for different durations (n = 4). **C** RT-qPCR analysis of DECR1 mRNA expression in HVSMCs. HVSMCs were cultured in CM or CM with 1 μ M UA for 1, 2, or 3 days (n = 4). **D** Representative western blot showing DECR1 expression in HVSMCs, with quantification by densitometry. HVSMCs were cultured in GM with 50 μ M CHX, with or without 1 μ M UA for different durations (n = 4). **E** Representative western blots showing ubiquitin-DECR1 and DECR1 expression in coimmunoprecipitation assay of DECR1 and ubiquitin in HEK293T cells, with quantification by densitometry (n = 4). HEK293T Cells transfected with Flag-DECR1 plasmid and Myc-ubiquitin plasmid were cultured with or without 1 μ M UA for 2 days. The lysates were immunoprecipitated with anti-Flag magnetic beads, and the precipitates were analyzed by immunoblotting with anti-Myc antibody. **F** Representative western blot showing DECR1 expression in HVSMCs, with quantification by densitometry. HVSMCs were cultured in GM with 1 μ M UA, with or without 100 nM MG132 for 4 days (n = 4). **G** Calcium deposition in HVSMCs was detected with alizarin red staining. Scale bar = 500 μ M. HVSMCs transfected with Ad/GFP were cultured in GM or CM, while those transfected with Ad/DECR1 were cultured in CM in the absence or presence of UA (G–I, n = 4). **H** Quantification of calcium content using a calcium assay kit. **I** Representative western blots showing RUNX2, BMP2, and α -SMA in HVSMCs, with quantification by densitometry. **J** Representative western blot showing DECR1 expression in rat aortas, with quantification by densitometry (n=6). **K** Representative immunohistochemistry images of Decr1 in rat aortas, with quantification by integrated option density (IOD, n = 12). Scale bars = 200 μ m (upper) or 50 μ m (lower). Data were presented as mean \pm SD. Two-tailed Student unpaired t-test for C, E. One-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's test for A, B, F, and J. Kruskal-Wallis test followed by Dunn's test for K. Two-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni test for D, H, and I. * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001, ns not significant. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Ursolic acid inhibits vascular calcification via downregulating NF- κ B/NLRP3 signaling pathway

To elucidate the downstream mechanisms by which UA inhibits vascular calcification through DEC1, we performed RNA sequencing in HVSMCs treated with or without UA in the presence of CM. KEGG enrichment analysis revealed that the differentially expressed genes were related to NF- κ B signaling pathways (Fig. 7A). Considering the link between inflammation and vascular calcification, and the anti-inflammatory activity of UA, we focused on vascular inflammation. Our previous study demonstrated that the NF- κ B/NLRP3 signaling pathway plays a crucial role in vascular calcification^{16,57}. Of interest, our study found that compared to GM-treated HVSMCs, the protein levels of phospho-NF- κ B (p-p65) were increased in CM-treated HVSMCs, but UA treatment decreased p-p65 levels and the p-p65/p65 ratio (Fig. 7B). Additionally, under osteogenic conditions, the p65 unit of NF- κ B translocated from the cytosol to the nucleus, which was prevented by UA treatment (Fig. 7C). This suggests that UA inactivates NF- κ B signaling during VSMC calcification. Western blot analysis also showed that CM increased the protein levels of NLRP3, cleaved Caspase-1, IL-1 β , and these molecules were further decreased after UA treatment (Fig. 7D). Consistently, the ratios of cleaved Caspase-1/Caspase-1 and IL-1 β /pro-IL-1 β were reduced by UA treatment. Furthermore, the NLRP3 inflammasome agonist Nigericin blocked the inhibitory effect of UA on vascular calcification and prevented the downregulation of RUNX2 and BMP2, as well as the upregulation of α -SMA protein expression (Fig. 7E–G).

Furthermore, the p-p65 and NLRP3 protein levels were increased in the aortas of CKD rats, and UA administration decreased p-p65 and NLRP3 levels as well as the p-p65/p65 ratio (Fig. 7H). Immunofluorescence analysis further showed that UA inhibited the nuclear translocation of NF- κ B in aortic medial layer (Fig. 7I). In summary, these results indicate that UA inhibits vascular calcification via downregulating NF- κ B/NLRP3 signaling pathway.

Figure 7

Fig. 7 UA inhibits vascular calcification via downregulating NF-κB/NLRP3 signaling pathway. **A** Enrichment analysis of differential expressed genes using the Hallmark gene set to evaluate changes in signal transduction following UA treatment. HVSMCs were cultured in calcifying medium (CM) or CM with 1 μM UA for 2 days, followed by RNA sequencing analysis (n=3). **B** Representative western blots showing phosphorylated p65 (p-p65) and total p65 in HVSMCs, with quantification by densitometry. HVSMCs were cultured in growth medium (GM), CM or CM with 1 μM UA for 7 days (B–D, n = 4). **C** Representative immunofluorescence images of p65 in HVSMCs, with quantification by mean fluorescence intensity (MFI, n = 25). Scale bar = 5 μM. **D** Representative western blots showing NLRP3,

cleaved Caspase-1, Caspase-1, IL-1 β , and pro-IL-1 β in HVSMCs, with quantification by densitometry. **E** Calcium deposition in HVSMCs was detected with alizarin red staining. Scale bar = 500 μ M. HVSMCs were cultured in GM, CM, CM with 1 μ M UA, or CM with 1 μ M UA and 5 μ M nigericin (Nig, E–G, n = 4). **F** Quantification of calcium content using a calcium assay kit. **G** Representative western blots showing RUNX2, BMP2, and α -SMA in HVSMCs, with quantification by densitometry. **H** Representative western blots showing p-p65 and p65 in rat aortas, with quantification by densitometry. **I** Representative immunofluorescence images of p65 in rat aortas, with quantification by MFI (n = 25). Scale bar = 50 μ M. Data were presented as mean \pm SD. One-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni test for B, D, and H. Kruskal-Wallis test followed by Dunn's test for C and I. Two-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni test for F and G. * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Ursolic acid relies on DECR1 to regulate NF- κ B/NLRP3 signaling pathway and inhibit vascular calcification

Next, we investigated whether DECR1 plays a role in the inhibitory effect of UA on NF- κ B/NLRP3 pathway in VSMCs. Western blot analysis showed that the downregulation of p-p65 by UA was partially reversed by DECR1 overexpression (Fig. 8A). Similarly, UA inhibited the translocation of p65 from the cytoplasm to the nucleus, and this effect was antagonized by DECR1 overexpression (Fig. 8B). Additionally, the inhibitory effect of UA on the ratios of cleaved Caspase-1/Caspase-1 and IL-1 β /pro-IL-1 β was also reversed by DECR1 overexpression (Fig. 8C), suggesting that UA inhibits the NF- κ B/NLRP3 signaling pathway through the downregulation of DECR1. Moreover, DECR1 knockdown significantly inhibited NF- κ B/NLRP3 pathway in CM-treated HVSMCs (Supplementary Fig. 8). These results indicate that DECR1 is an upstream regulator of the NF- κ B/NLRP3 pathway in HVSMCs. Furthermore, UA treatment reduced VSMC calcification, but this effect was prevented by Ad/DECR1. Furthermore, the NLRP3 inhibitor MCC950 counteracted the pro-calcification effect of Ad-DECR1 (Fig. 8D). Cells treated with MCC950 exhibited lower calcium levels compared to those treated with UA and Ad/DECR1 under osteogenic conditions (Fig. 8E). Western blot analysis also demonstrated that Ad/DECR1 prevented the inhibition of VSMC

osteogenic differentiation by UA, and this prevention was reversed by MCC950 (Fig. 8F). These findings indicate that UA alleviates VSMC calcification through DECR1-mediated inhibition of the NF- κ B/NLRP3 signaling pathway.

Figure 8

Fig. 8 UA relies on DECR1 to regulate NF- κ B/NLRP3 signaling pathway and inhibit vascular calcification. **A** Representative western blots showing phosphorylated p65 (p-p65) and total p65 in HVSMCs, with quantification by densitometry. HVSMCs transfected with Ad/GFP were cultured in growth medium (GM) or calcifying medium (CM), while those transfected with Ad/DECR1 were cultured in CM in the absence or presence of UA (A–C, n = 4). **B** Representative immunofluorescence images of p65 in HVSMCs, with quantification by mean fluorescence intensity (MFI, n = 25). Scale bar = 5 μ m. **C** Representative western blots showing NLRP3, cleaved Caspase-1, Caspase-1, IL-1 β , and pro-IL-1 β in HVSMCs, with

quantification by densitometry. **D** Calcium deposition in HVSMCs was detected with alizarin red staining. Scale bar = 500 μ M. HVSMCs transfected with Ad/GFP were cultured in GM, CM, or CM with 1 μ M UA, while those transfected with Ad/DEC1 in CM with 1 μ M (D–F, n = 4). **E** Quantification of calcium content using a calcium assay kit. **F** Representative western blots showing RUNX2, BMP2, and α -SMA in HVSMCs, with quantification by densitometry. Data were presented as mean \pm SD. Two-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni test for A, and C. Kruskal-Wallis test followed by Dunn’s test for B. Three-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni test for D–F. * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Discussion

Vascular calcification is a common complication in CKD, contributing to the increased rates of cardiovascular events and overall mortality^{58,59}. However, safe and effective treatments for vascular calcification remain lacking. Our findings provide compelling evidence that UA effectively inhibits vascular calcification using both *in vitro* and *in vivo* models. Mechanistically, our results demonstrate that UA directly interacts with DEC1. This interaction promotes the degradation of DEC1 via the ubiquitin-proteasome system (UPS). Subsequently, UA-induced degradation of DEC1 inhibits the NF- κ B/NLRP3 pathway and leads to the suppression of vascular calcification. This study for the first time demonstrates that UA inhibits vascular calcification and elucidates the role of DEC1 in this process, providing valuable insights into potential therapeutic strategies.

Ursolic acid, a naturally occurring triterpenoid compound, is found in various medicinal plants such as apple peels, rosemary, oregano, and marjoram⁶⁰. It has garnered significant attention due to its diverse biological activities, including anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anticancer, and metabolic regulatory effects⁶¹. Notably, its anti-inflammatory properties are particularly pronounced¹⁹. Recent studies have shown that UA alleviates chronic prostatitis by regulating the NLRP3 inflammasome-mediated Caspase-1/GSDMD pyroptosis pathway, and it reduces neuroinflammation following intracerebral hemorrhage by mediating microglial pyroptosis via the NF- κ B/NLRP3/GSDMD pathway. UA primarily targets NF- κ B to regulate inflammation,

inhibiting its activation by suppressing I κ B kinase and p65 phosphorylation⁶². Furthermore, increasing evidence has highlighted the therapeutic effects of ursolic acid in age-related diseases such as vascular aging⁶³⁻⁶⁵. Additionally, oral administration of ursolic acid has been shown to extend the lifespan of male *Drosophila melanogaster* and *Caenorhabditis elegans*^{66,67}. As is well known, aging and inflammation are significant risk factors for medial arterial calcification⁶⁸. However, the role of UA in the progression of vascular calcification remains to be explored. In our study, we found that UA significantly reduced calcification in VSMCs and arterial rings under osteogenic conditions *in vitro*. Furthermore, *in vivo* experiments demonstrated significantly lower aortic calcification in both CKD rats and vitamin D3-overloaded mice following UA treatment. These results suggest that UA effectively prevent vascular calcification.

Natural products hold obvious advantages in drug discovery due to their structural complexity, functional diversity, adaptability, biocompatibility, and pharmacokinetic characteristics in comparison with conventional synthetic small-molecule drugs⁶⁹. Among the small-molecule drugs approved by the Food and Drug Administration, 63.1% of the drugs were directly or indirectly derived from natural products⁷⁰. UA, a naturally occurring pentacyclic triterpenoid, is the major waxy component in apple peels and founded in various food and medicinal herbs⁷¹. As a food-derived natural compound, UA has a long history of human consumption, with an apple alone containing hundreds mg of this compound, underscoring its favorable safety profile⁷². In our study, we found that UA effectively inhibits vascular inflammation and calcification without causing significant toxicity, as indicated by the absence of adverse changes in serum liver enzyme or body weight. Furthermore, its structural isomer, oleanolic acid, has been used in the clinic as a hepatoprotective medicine in China since 1970s, and no serious adverse reactions have been reported⁷³. Beyond its role in vascular calcification, UA has demonstrated additional benefits on muscle wasting, osteoporosis, and renal fibrosis in animal models⁷⁴⁻⁷⁶. This suggests that UA may have potential therapeutic effects on various CKD-related complications, and minimize the side effects associated with polypharmacy. This multifaceted therapeutic approach positions UA as a promising candidate for the development of new treatments targeting both vascular calcification and other CKD-related comorbidities.

Despite its known anti-inflammatory effects, the direct targets of UA remain unclear. In our study, we applied CETSA to confirm the in-situ binding of UA to DECR1 within cells. This was further corroborated by purified protein, cell lysates, and tissue samples, validating the direct interaction between DECR1 and UA both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. These results provide compelling evidence that DECR1 is a direct target of UA in the context of vascular calcification. Typically, drug binding increases protein thermal stability, but in some cases, it can decrease stability, often due to the drug interacting with a less stable protein conformation⁷⁷. Our findings revealed that UA reduced DECR1's thermal stability within cells, suggesting that it may bind to a less stable conformation of DECR1. This interaction may promote protein denaturation during CETSA's heating steps. This reduced stability could be linked to the ubiquitin-mediated degradation of DECR1, where UA binding triggers a conformational change that enables the protein to be recognized by the cellular quality control system, leading to its degradation.

Recognized for its anti-inflammatory properties, UA is a promising natural compound for treating cardiovascular diseases⁷⁸. NLRP3 inflammasome is implicated in numerous vascular diseases, such as hypertension, atherosclerosis, vascular injury, and aortic aneurysm⁷⁹⁻⁸². Recent evidence links the NLRP3 inflammasome to regulation of vascular calcification. Agents like irisin, puerarin, and sodium-glucose cotransporter 2 inhibitors reducing vascular calcification by inhibiting NLRP3^{57,83-85}. In contrast, trimethylamine N-oxide accelerates it by activating NLRP3¹⁶. Our findings suggest that UA could similarly attenuate vascular calcification by targeting NLRP3 inflammasome. This study demonstrated that UA suppresses the NF- κ B/NLRP3 signaling pathway and downstream inflammatory molecules Caspase-1 and IL-1 β , which is a key mediator of inflammatory vascular calcification⁸⁶. Additionally, the inhibitory effects of UA on vascular calcification were reversed by NLRP3 agonists, underscoring that UA reduce vascular calcification via NLRP3/Caspase-1/IL-1 β pathway.

Our research identified DECR1 as a direct target of UA, mediating its inhibitory effect on the NF- κ B/NLRP3 pathway and vascular calcification. However, although this study shows that DECR1 influences NF- κ B/NLRP3 pathway, the precise molecular mechanisms remain unclear.

DECR1 may modulate intracellular unsaturated fatty acid levels, influencing lipid mediators like Resolvin D1 and specialized pro-resolving mediators. Free fatty acid receptor 4 (FFAR4), a receptor for long-chain fatty acids including omega-3 PUFAs, is found to mediate EPA's protection to vascular calcification in *klotho* mutant mice⁸⁷. Furthermore, FFAR4 also implicated in omega-3 fatty acids' anti-vascular inflammation⁸⁸. DECR1 may affect NF- κ B/NLRP3 pathway through metabolic interactions with FFAR4.

In conclusion, our study shows that UA effectively inhibits vascular calcification both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. This protective effect is mediated through the induction of DECR1 ubiquitin-proteasome degradation, leading to the suppression of the NF- κ B/NLRP3 signaling pathway. These findings highlight the potential of UA as a promising candidate for developing new therapeutic strategies against vascular calcification, with DECR1 inhibition emerging as a valuable target for prevention. UA may serve as a compound for the development of novel small molecules, and targeting DECR1 with these small molecules presents an ideal opportunity for translating these findings into clinical applications for combating vascular calcification.

Data availability

The RNA-seq data generated in this study have been deposited in the NCBI GEO database under accession code GSE276910. Additional RNA-seq data were downloaded from Gene Expression Omnibus (GSE146638 and GSE211722). Additional proteome data were downloaded from ProteomeXchange database (PXD022575, PXD030975 and PXD039077). Additional data related to this paper are available from the corresponding author on request. Source data are provided with this paper.

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Contributions

Hongwei Yang contributed substantially to this work by conducting all the experiments, collecting and analyzing the data, and preparing the initial draft of the results section. Zirong Lan participated in the revision process, provided critical feedback on the manuscript. Jianyun Yan provided the essential experimental facilities, secured the research funding, offered overall academic guidance, and supervised the entire research project.

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Supplementary data

Supplementary figure 1

Supplementary Fig. 1 Preliminary experiments investigate UA's effect on viability of HVSMCs. **A** Quantification of CCK8 cell viability assay to assess the effect of UA on viability of HVSMCs. HVSMCs were cultured in growth medium (GM) with UA (0–50 μM) for 4 days (n = 4). Data were presented as mean ± SD. One-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni test for **B**. *** p < 0.001. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Supplementary figure 2

Supplementary Fig. 2 UA administration did not induce significant systemic toxicity in CKD rats. **A** Quantification of serum ALT and AST of CKD rats. Rats subjected to 5/6 nephrectomy were treated with vehicle or UA (80 mg/kg/day) intragastrically for 4 weeks (n = 6) **B** Quantification of body weight of rats. Data were presented as mean ± SD. Two-tailed Student unpaired t-test for **A**. Two-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni test for **B**. ns not

significant. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Supplementary figure 3

Supplementary Fig. 3 ITDR-CETSA evaluates UA's occupancy of intracellular targets.

Representative western blots of ITDR-CETSA showing UA binding to DECR1 and HIBCH in living cells, with quantification by densitometry. HVSMCs were incubated with 0–1 mM UA for 1 h and heated at 62 °C (n = 4). EC_{50} , median effective concentration. Data were presented as mean \pm SD. One-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni test for B. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Supplementary figure 4

Supplementary Fig. 4 Dynamics simulations indicates that UA remains stably bound to DECR1. **A** Root mean square deviation (RMSD) of the DECR1-UA complex and UA. **B** Root mean square fluctuation (RMSF) of DECR1 within the complex. **C** The radius of gyration (Rg) of the complex. **D** Buried solvent accessible surface area (Buried SASA) between UA and DECR1. **E** Contribution of each amino acid to the complex's binding energy.

Supplementary figure 5

Supplementary Fig. 5 DECR1 mRNA expression is not elevated in vascular calcification despite increased protein levels. **A** RT-qPCR analysis of DECR1 mRNA expression in HVSMCs. HVSMCs were cultured in growth medium (GM) or calcifying medium (CM) for 1, 3, or 5 days (n = 4). **B** Quantification of DECR1 mRNA in rats of control group and uremic group based on RNA-sequencing dataset GSE146638 from GEO database (n = 5). **C** Quantification of DECR1 mRNA in human coronary artery smooth muscle cells (HCASMCs) based on RNA-sequencing dataset GSE211722 from GEO dataset. HCASMCs were cultured in normal medium (NM) or osteogenic medium (OM) for 7 days (n = 2). Data were presented as mean \pm SD. Two-tailed Student unpaired t-test for A and C. Mann-Whitney test for B. * p < 0.05, *** p < 0.001, ns not significant. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Supplementary figure 6

Supplementary Fig. 6 Chloroquine (CQ) treatment did not block the UA-induced DECR1 degradation. Representative western blot showing DECR1 expression in HVSMCs, with quantification by densitometry. HVSMCs were cultured in growth medium (GM) with 1 μ M UA, with or without 20 μ M CQ for 4 days (n = 4). Data were presented as mean \pm SD. One-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni test. *** p < 0.001, ns not significant. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Supplementary figure 7

Supplementary Fig. 7 Washout experiment demonstrates the reversibility of UA-induced DECR1 degradation. Representative western blot showing DECR1 expression in HVSMCs, with quantification by densitometry. HVSMCs were cultured in growth medium (GM) with 1 μ M UA for 72 h, followed by a washout and subsequent culture for an additional 12 or 24 h. Data were presented as mean \pm SD. One-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni test. ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, ns not significant. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Supplementary figure 8

Supplementary Fig. 8 DECR1 knockdown inhibits NF- κ B/NLRP3 signaling pathway. A Representative western blots showing phosphorylated p65 (p-p65) and total p65 in HVSMCs, with quantification by densitometry. After transfection with negative control siRNA (si-NC) or DECR1 siRNA (si-DECR1), HVSMCs were cultured in growth medium (GM) or calcifying medium (CM) for 7 days ($n = 4$). **B** Representative immunofluorescence images of p65 in HVSMCs, with quantification by mean fluorescence intensity (MFI, $n = 25$). Scale bar = 5 μ M. **C** Representative western blots showing NLRP3, cleaved Caspase-1, Caspase-1, IL-1 β , and pro-IL-1 β in HVSMCs, with quantification by densitometry. Data were presented as mean \pm SD.

Two-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni test. ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, ns not significant.

Source data are provided as a Source Data file.